

Original Research

The Impact of Financial Development on Private Sector Growth in the Oil-Based Economy of Iraq

Ali Saeed Shekar Elwandi

Department of Economics, Isf.C., Islamic Azad University, Isfahan, Iran

Maryam Emamimibody¹

Department of Accounting, Shahi.c., Islamic Azad University, Shahinshahr, Iran

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Abstract

The main objective of this study is to examine the impact of financial development on private sector growth in Iraq's oil-based economy. To test the hypotheses, the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) was employed to estimate the research model over the period from 2008 to 2022. The estimation results reveal a significant positive relationship between financial development indicators and private sector growth. Specifically, the ratio of the total money supply to GDP and the value of stock market transactions—both indicators of financial development—contribute to increased private sector growth in Iraq. In this context, it is essential to establish the necessary institutional conditions and a conducive environment to support the financial development process and thereby enhance the potential for private sector growth. However, the ratio of credit to the private sector to GDP, used as a measure of financial depth, was found to have a positive but statistically insignificant effect on private sector growth. This suggests that Iraqi banks have not played an effective role in supporting the private sector. Therefore, the Central Bank should adopt cautious and well-targeted monetary policies, leveraging oil revenues to promote coherence and integration within financial markets and to create the necessary environment for strengthening formal financial institutions in Iraq.

Keywords: Financial Development, Oil-based Economy, Private Sector Growth.

¹ Corresponding author's Email: m.emamimibodi@yahoo.com

Introduction

Financial development plays a crucial role in economic growth, as it contributes to the accumulation of savings and facilitates capital formation. This process enhances both the quantity and quality of financial intermediation services. The role of financial intermediaries includes mobilizing and pooling investment funds, as well as ensuring the efficient allocation of resources, selection and screening of projects, risk management, corporate governance, and oversight of business operations within the framework of a national financial system. In fact, the modern financial environment encompasses a wide range of activities, including trade facilitation, risk aggregation, risk hedging, and other related functions. Essentially, an efficient financial system fosters a productive investment environment, which leads to improved macroeconomic performance and supports long-term economic growth. The relationship between financial development and economic growth was first examined by Schumpeter (1911), who demonstrated that the financial system acts as a catalyst for technological innovation and, ultimately, economic development. Subsequent studies by Robinson (1952) and McKinnon (1973) also confirmed a positive relationship between financial development and economic progress. These studies laid the groundwork for the financial liberalization hypothesis, advocating for the reduction of governmental constraints in order to encourage investment. Greenwood and Jovanovic (1990), in their endogenous growth theory, argue that financial development has a positive impact on sustainable economic growth (King and Levine, 1993).

According to Patrick (1966), two perspectives are presented regarding the relationship between economic growth and the financial sector. The first is the demand-driven perspective, while the second is supply-driven. The demand-driven perspective suggests that as the real economy grows and the demand for financial services increases within society, financial services expand accordingly. In contrast, the supply-driven perspective posits that the provision of financial services drives economic growth. From this viewpoint, the availability of funds through financial institutions enables entrepreneurs and economic agents to assume greater levels of debt and undertake more productive investments at the societal level. Therefore, increasing the mobilization of deposits and lending activities is a key component of financial intermediation, as it stimulates investment within the community. Financial intermediation, in turn, has the potential to enhance the economy's productive capacity. According to Rousseau and Wachtel (1998), the impact of financial development on economic growth is positive, as financial intermediation improves investment efficiency, thereby leading to higher per capita GDP growth rates (Krishnankutty, 2011).

On the other hand, in the empirical literature, there are several perspectives regarding the relationship between financial development and economic growth. Researchers such as De Gregorio and Kim (2000), Christopoulos and Tsionas (2004), and Hamdi (2015) argue that financial development influences economic growth. Conversely, Rajan and Zingales (1998), Al-Yousif (2002), Al-Malkawi et al. (2012), and Grassa and Gazdar (2014) contend that economic growth drives financial development. Some scholars, including Greenwood and Smith (1997) and Abu-Bader and Abu-Qarn (2008), suggest that there is a bidirectional relationship between financial development and economic growth. Another group of researchers, such as Stern (1989) and Loayza and Ranciere

(2006), argue that financial development and economic growth do not significantly affect each other. However, financial development plays a distinct role in oil-rich economies, as it can help mitigate the "resource curse" by channeling oil revenues into more productive and sustainable economic activities (Law and Moradbeigi, 2017).

According to studies by Lohmann (1992) and Greenwood et al. (1997), the demand for funds to finance production and facilitate capital accumulation—particularly in the private sector—and the subsequent development of the financial sector are crucial. Furthermore, the development of the financial sector, especially banks and stock markets, plays a significant role in financing companies (Demirgüç-Kunt and Maksimovic, 1996). The private sector benefits from financial development not only through the mobilization of savings and the organization of transactions, but also by gaining access to funding for research, corporate governance, and risk management (Levine, 2005).

In completing the description, the innovation of this research lies in its use of the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) to analyze the impact of financial development on private sector growth in Iraq's oil-based economy. Additionally, it identifies the nuanced role of various financial indicators, such as the money supply-to-GDP ratio and stock market transactions, in promoting private sector growth while highlighting the limited effectiveness of credit to the private sector in this context. Based on the discussions concerning the impact of financial development on private sector growth, the aim of this paper is to examine the effect of financial development on private sector growth in an oil-based economy, using Iraq as a case study. The paper begins with a review of the theoretical foundations and relevant literature, followed by the research methodology, presentation of findings, and, finally, the conclusions and recommendations.

Theoretical Foundations

Financial Development

Following the 1970s and the evolution of financial markets, the concept of financial development emerged as a response to financial repression. The performance of the financial system influences the behavior of consumers, investors, and producers—groups that collectively contribute to total economic output. Economists' perspectives on the importance of financial development can generally be classified into two main theoretical approaches. The first group, including economists such as Modigliani, Miller, and Lucas, did not assign significant importance to the financial sector. In contrast, the second group places considerable emphasis on financial development and can be further divided into two schools of thought:

- Keynesian economists, who advocate for government intervention in financial markets and support the imposition of interest rate ceilings, and
- Neoclassical economists, who favor interest rate liberalization policies.

In the 1980s, with the rise of new institutional financial theory, the Keynesian general theory was largely set aside (Levine, 2004). As a result, financial development is now understood as a multidimensional concept comprising six components:

1. Development of the banking sector
2. Development of the non-banking financial sector
3. Development of monetary policy and policymaking institutions
4. Banking regulations and supervision
5. Openness of the financial sector
6. The institutional environment (Yavari et al., 2011).

Financial Development Indicators

Levine et al. (2000) introduced the following variables to measure financial development:

1. The ratio of financial system debt and cash liabilities to GDP.
2. The ratio of bank credit to the sum of bank credit and central bank assets.
3. The ratio of credit allocated to private companies and institutions to total domestic credit (excluding credit to banks).
4. The ratio of credit provided to private companies and institutions to GDP.
5. The ratio of long-term and demand deposit savings in deposit-taking banks and other financial institutions to GDP, as well as the ratio of money and quasi-money (M2) to GDP (Zarei and Lajevardi, 2018).

The financial system of countries can generally be classified as either **market-based** or **bank-based**. A financial system is considered bank-based if banks play the dominant role in financing. In most developing countries, the banking sector is the most important component of the money market. The main indicators of financial development in the banking sector include:

1. The ratio of deposits in non-government banks to total deposits in the banking network.
2. The ratio of private sector debt owed to non-government banks to total private sector debt.
3. The share of credit allocated to the private sector out of total credit (a higher share indicates a more effective financial system in supporting investment, managing risk, and providing financial services).

4. The ratio of domestic bank assets (excluding those of the central bank) to the total assets of the banking system (including the central bank).
5. The degree of bank concentration: a high concentration ratio suggests limited competition and inefficiency in the banking network.
6. The efficiency of the banking network: measured by the loan-to-deposit ratio, which reflects the ability of the financial system to utilize deposits for lending purposes (Shams Al-Harrafard et al., 2020).

According to the study by Rioja and Kroszner (2006), the following indicators are also used to measure financial development:

1. Private Sector Credit Index – This includes the total value of credit allocated by financial intermediaries to the private sector as a percentage of GDP. It reflects financial depth and size (e.g., liquidity commitments or outstanding debt), and financial completeness, which is derived from the market value of publicly traded stocks.
2. Market Value Index – This refers to the total market capitalization of listed domestic shares as a percentage of GDP.
3. Funds Value Ratio Index – This measures the ratio of the total value of domestic stock market transactions to the market capitalization of listed stocks.
4. Traded Value Index – This indicates the ratio of the value of shares traded on the domestic stock market to GDP (Loghmani Devin, 2015).

However, in market-based theory, the performance of financial markets is considered superior to that of bank-based systems. In a market-based financial system, a large and liquid capital market is established within society. With the advancement of profit motives and corporate governance mechanisms, risk management becomes more attainable (Aboutoraby et al., 2013).

Effects of Financial Development on the Private Sector in Economic Conditions

From the perspective of the new institutional financial theory, two models are presented: the risk and credit intermediation costs model and the credit rationing model. In both models, the total level of credit in the economy is determined by the fundamental characteristics of borrowers and lenders. In the credit risk and intermediation costs model, financial variables play a key role in the supply of credit, and the cost of financial intermediation becomes a critical factor. In addition to interest payments, borrowers must bear various intermediation costs, including those related to information provision, collateral requirements, deposited funds, property appraisals, financial evaluations, and credit history assessments. High intermediation costs often lead firms to prefer internal financing over external credit for investment purposes. During economic recessions when business sales decline and the risk of bankruptcy increases the cost of obtaining credit also rises. Lenders respond to heightened risk by demanding higher interest rates or more stringent collateral and information requirements, thereby increasing intermediation costs. Under such conditions, many businesses are unable to access the necessary credit,

leading to reduced investment and consumption demand, which in turn deepens the economic downturn. Simultaneously, banks and credit institutions, facing an increased risk of loan defaults, adopt risk-averse policies. They focus on maintaining higher levels of liquid assets, further raising credit intermediation costs and reducing the efficiency of lending. This exacerbates the recession, creating a feedback loop known as the financial accelerator model. In contrast, the credit rationing model, which highlights credit constraints, underscores the role of asymmetric and heterogeneous information between lenders and borrowers. Due to incomplete information, lenders face uncertainty about borrowers' default risks, leading to divergent expectations regarding each borrower's creditworthiness. Moreover, the presence of credit risk and the stickiness of interest rates caused by lenders' reluctance to adjust rates frequently result in persistent market imbalances. Consequently, fluctuations in financial markets and shifts in core financial variables lead to changes in lending behavior, investment, and consumption across the economy. In recessionary conditions, repayment risk rises, prompting lenders to reduce credit supply especially to borrowers with lower or more volatile net worth or liquidity. As a result, such businesses face greater difficulty accessing credit during downturns (Noop, 2017).

Financial Development in an Oil-Based Economy

In non-oil economies, the financial sector supports the mobilization and management of savings and provides essential financial services to the economy. However, in oil-based economies, oil revenue serves as an additional source of income that is injected into the financial sector, effectively replacing community savings. This substitution leads to significant fluctuations in the general price level and, consequently, reduces the efficiency of investment projects. In other words, in oil-dependent economies, oil revenue plays a double-edged sword role. On one hand, increased oil revenues have a substantial impact on national income and play a crucial role in infrastructure development. On the other hand, the misallocation of this national wealth across various economic sectors leads to severe price volatility, market imbalances, rent-seeking behavior, and a disrupted development trajectory—a phenomenon commonly referred to as the "resource curse" (Moradbeigi and Law, 2016).

The resource curse refers to the distortion of incentives for investment in institutions, education, and other public services, resulting from the windfall wealth generated by natural resources. In the short term, this phenomenon negatively affects political stability and limits the freedom to formulate sound economic policies. This is because reliance on natural resources reduces the need for investment in specialized markets, human capital, and research and development activities. In the long run, it diminishes the incentive for community-level investment in institutional structures that support broad-based market transactions, the protection of private property rights, and a contractual framework essential for non-commodity production (Besley and Persson, 2010). In oil-based economies, dependence on natural resources often results in governments that are less inclined to compromise with opposition parties, evade accountability, and resist transparency. The use of natural resource revenues in such political systems can hinder development by shifting the focus from productive entrepreneurship to rent-seeking behavior (Aboutoraby et al., 2013).

Previous Research

Nguyen et al. (2025), In an article titled *Energy Diversification, Financial Development, and Economic Development*, the factors affecting convergence in OECD countries were examined using Granger causality tests and panel regressions over the period from 1997 to 2021. The findings of the study revealed that the Granger causality tests indicated short-run bidirectional relationships between the variables. The long-run panel regression analysis confirmed that technological progress significantly improves both per capita income and energy diversification. Furthermore, bidirectional relationships between energy diversification and financial development were identified, along with a unidirectional relationship from financial development to per capita income, and a U-shaped effect of per capita income on energy diversification, with a turning point at \$67,112.8 per year.

He and Yoo (2024), A study titled *The Impact of Financial Development on Domestic Investment Considering the Role of Income Level* using the GMM panel model in 152 countries over the period from 1980 to 2021 revealed that financial development has a positive effect on investment performance, provided it does not exceed a certain threshold. However, while increasing financial development benefits investment, further deepening of the financial sector may ultimately reduce its impact on domestic investment. Specifically, the benefit of investment growth is valid only up to the threshold of 0.5147, beyond which it becomes a constraint. In the short term, changes in financial development do not have a significant impact on investment. Moreover, the marginal effect of financial development on investment is more pronounced in low- and middle-income countries.

Ahmad (2023), in an article titled *The Role of the Central Bank of Iraq in Promoting Financial Inclusion in Iraq during the Years 2016–2020*, analytically examines the promotion of financial inclusion. The study highlights that the most important strategy of the Central Bank of Iraq is focusing on financial inclusion. This is because the development of banking services plays a fundamental role in combating poverty, improving the standard of living for citizens, and achieving stability and economic development in Iraq.

Jasim and Nazeer (2023), in an article titled *The Impact of Banking Sector Development on Economic Growth in Iraq Using the ARDL Method during the Period 2004–2021*, examined the research hypotheses. The findings revealed that the banking sector in Iraq faces multiple challenges. These weaknesses, which have prevented the sector from fully realizing its potential, include issues such as lack of coverage, banking for the population, limited financial support for small and medium-sized enterprises, and a low level of technological development and innovation in banking services in Iraq.

Alavi et al. (2022), in an article titled *Assessing the Impact of Financial Development on Economic Growth in Iran: Testing Patrick's Hypotheses for the Period 1978–2019 Using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag Method*, found that the effect of the banking deposit volume variable on the financial development index was greater than that of other financial variables. Additionally, the financial development index had a positive relationship with economic growth in both the short and long term. Patrick's hypothesis

test confirmed the demand-following view, which indicates causality from economic growth to financial development.

Lwesya and Ismail (2021), in an article titled *Financial Development and Private Sector Investment in the Post-Liberalization Era in Tanzania Using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag Method*, concluded that the financial market depth index had a positive and significant impact on private sector investment in the long term. This is related to the current underdevelopment of capital markets in Tanzania. The degree of openness of the economy had a positive and significant effect on private investment in both periods, indicating its important role in financial development and private sector growth in Tanzania. Conversely, the real exchange rate had a negative and significant impact on private investment in both the short and long term, indicating that an increase in the real exchange rate has a negative impact on private sector investment.

Imdadul Haque (2020), in an article titled *Private Sector Growth and Financial Development in Saudi Arabia Using the Vector Autoregression Method for the Period 1985–2018*, found that GDP in the private sector had a negative relationship with the money supply, a positive relationship with bank credit to the private sector, and no significant relationship with stock market values. Furthermore, private sector growth had a positive and significant relationship with government expenditures, investments, and trade openness.

Based on the explanations in the theoretical background and the main objective of this research, which is to examine the effects of equilibrium exchange rate deviations on Iraq's foreign trade, the following two hypotheses have been tested:

H₁: The impact of financial development indicators on private sector growth in Iraq is significant.

H₂: The impact of financial depth on private sector growth in Iraq is significant.

Research Methodology

The research method is of a correlational causal type, based on time series data analysis. The aim of this research is to present a macroeconomic model considering the specific conditions of Iraq. The research data was collected in a library-based, documentary manner from the World Bank database for the period 2008-2022 for Iraq. Since macroeconomic indicators for Iraq are only available on an annual basis on the World Bank website, and to avoid issues related to insufficient degrees of freedom in estimating the model, all data were converted into quarterly data using the Chow and Lin method² with the EViews software. To analyze the impact of financial development on private sector growth in an oil-based economy, the study employs the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM). The model used in this research is based on the study by Imdadul Haque (2020), which was conducted for Saudi Arabia, a country with similar

² - The Chow-Lin method in econometrics is used as a data homogenization technique to convert annual data into quarterly data, based on time-series models. Since this method can more accurately simulate seasonal fluctuations, it is essential for econometric analyses that require quarterly data, as it enhances the accuracy of modeling and estimating economic relationships.

characteristics to Iraq as an Arab oil-exporting nation. Therefore, due to these similarities, the aforementioned research model was estimated for Iraq. The research model is as follows:

$$\ln PRGDP_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \ln M_t + \alpha_2 \ln BC_t + \alpha_3 \ln S_t + \alpha_4 \ln G_t + \alpha_5 \ln I_t + \alpha_6 \ln TO_t + \alpha_7 D_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

In which the dependent variable of the model is as follows: ($\ln PRGDP_t$), the logarithm of the ratio of private sector output to GDP is used as the representative of private sector growth. The independent variables are: ($\ln M_t$), ($\ln BC_t$) and ($\ln S_t$) in the model, they represent financial development, as explained below: ($\ln M_t$), the logarithm of the ratio of the total money supply to GDP is considered as a representative for financial development, according to the studies by Darrat et al. (2005), Masih et al. (2009), Samarkandi et al. (2014), Duasa (2014), Law and Moradbeygi (2017), and Rehman (2018). ($\ln BC_t$), the logarithm of the ratio of credit to the private sector to GDP. This variable is considered an effective and reliable measure of financial depth, as a developed financial system allocates more credit to the private sector (Beck, 2011). ($\ln S_t$), The logarithm of the stock market transaction value, a variable that is positively and strongly related to long-term economic growth, is considered as a representative for financial development according to the studies by Levine and Zervos (1998), Kouki (2013), and Ibrahim (2013).

However, the control variables in the model are as follows: ($\ln G_t$), the logarithm of the ratio of government consumption expenditure to GDP (Samarkandi et al., 2014). ($\ln I_t$), The logarithm of the ratio of private sector investment to GDP (Ibrahim, 2013). ($\ln TO_t$), The ratio of the trade balance to GDP, used as the trade openness variable (exports plus imports divided by GDP) (Grasa and Gazdar, 2014). (D_t), A dummy variable representing the critical period of the ISIS conflict (2014 to 2017).

Research Findings

Before estimating the model, it is necessary to check the stationarity of the variables in order to avoid the problem of spurious regression. Therefore, based on the results of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test, the variables of the research model in Table (1) are all non-stationary at the first level (I(1)). This confirms the validity of using the Error Correction Model (VECM).

Table 1. Results of Unit Root Test for Variables

Variable Symbol	Test Statistic	Significance Level	Unit Root Test Results
$\ln prGDp_t$	-7.485	0.0000	I(1)
$\ln M_t$	-8.118	0.0000	I(1)
$\ln BC_t$	-8.084	0.0000	I(1)
$\ln S_t$	-7.074	0.0000	I(1)
$\ln G_t$	-4.506	0.0070	I(1)
$\ln I_t$	-4.234	0.0140	I(1)
$\ln TO_t$	-4.051	0.0230	I(1)

To estimate the VECM model, it is necessary to perform diagnostic tests using the VAR method, followed by the estimation of the model using the VECM approach. This is because the VECM model is used to analyze the long-term and short-term relationships between non-stationary variables, especially when the variables exhibit cointegration. The model helps simulate long-term equilibrium and correct short-term deviations in economic relationships.

Diagnostic Tests

The next step after examining the stationarity of the variables is determining the optimal lag length, which can be done by using information criteria to select the order of the Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model. This method selects the number of lags from a set of possible lags in such a way that the critical value is minimized. In this context, due to the relatively small sample size, the Schwarz Information Criterion (SIC) is used. According to the results in Table (2), the optimal lag length for the model is two.

Table 2. Results of the Optimal Lag Length Selection Test

Lag	AIC	Schwarz	Hannan-Quinn
0	0.428	4.720	0.541
1	-0.454	5.174	0.562
2	1.622	*2.586	3.541
3	3.667	10.967	6.490
4	*-3.854	5.781	*-0.128

In the analysis of the Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model, it is essential to examine the stability of the model before analyzing the impulse response functions. As shown in Figure (1), the eigenvalues of the estimated model lie within the unit circle. Therefore, the model is considered stable.

Figure 1. Stability Check of the Model

In Table (3), the results of the diagnostic test for residuals are presented, checking for the assumptions of autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity in the model's residuals. According to the results in Table (3), the hypotheses of autocorrelation and

heteroscedasticity in the residuals are rejected, indicating that the estimation results are reliable.

Table 3. Diagnostic Tests for Residuals

Hypothesis	F-Statistic	Significance Probability
Breusch-Godfrey (LM) Autocorrelation Test	0.888	0.119
Breusch-Pagan Heteroscedasticity Test	1.351	0.247

In the next step, the convergence test for examining the non-stationary among the variables in the research model will be conducted using the Johansen test.

Table 4. Results of Johansson Test Model

Test Type	Intercept - No Trend	Intercept - No Trend	Intercept - No Trend	Intercept - With Trend	No Intercept - With Trend
Effect Matrix	1	0	1	0	1
Maximum Eigenvalues	1	0	0	0	0

Based on the results of the Johansson test in Table (4), the minimum non-zero maximum cointegration for long-term relationships in the research model occurs in the intercept - no trend condition. To complete the discussion on convergence, the eigenvalues and the effect matrix, as per the selected condition, are presented in Tables (5) and (6).

Table 5. Results of the Rank of the Effect Matrix Test for the Research Model

Hypothesis	Eigenvalues	Effect Matrix Statistic	Critical Value 0.05	P-Value
None	0.594	150.001	143.669	0.0208
At most 1	0.369	99.494	111.781	0.231
At most 2	0.312	73.691	83.937	0.219
At most 3	0.275	52.744	60.061	0.178
At most 4	0.247	34.727	40.175	0.159
At most 5	0.246	18.794	24.276	0.210
At most 6	0.051	2.957	12.321	0.853
At most 7	0.001	0.054	4.129	0.849

Based on the results in Table (5), for the research model, the statistic related to the effect matrix is 150.001, which is below 0.05, indicating the presence of one long-term convergence tendency.

However, the results in Table (6) show that for the research model, the statistic related to the maximum eigenvalues is 50.507, which is below 0.05, indicating the presence of one long-term convergence tendency. Finally, based on the results from both Tables (6) and (5), the long-term trend has been confirmed in the model, and the long-term relationships of the research model are interpreted in Table (7).

Table 6. Results of the Maximum Eigenvalue Rank Test for the Research Model

Hypothesis	Eigenvalues	Maximum Eigenvalue Statistic	Critical Value at 0.05	Significance Level
None	0.594	50.507	48.877	0.033
At most 1	0.369	25.803	42.772	0.850
At most 2	0.312	20.947	36.630	0.841
At most 3	0.275	18.017	30.439	0.697
At most 4	0.247	15.932	24.159	0.427
At most 5	0.246	15.837	17.797	0.096
At most 6	0.051	2.903	11.225	0.080
At most 7	0.001	0.054	4.129	0.849

Estimation of the Model Using the VECM Method

After estimating the VAR model and conducting diagnostic tests for the research hypotheses, the research model was estimated using the VECM method, and the results are presented in Table (7).

According to the results in Table (7), the impact of the logarithm of the total money supply/GDP ratio and the logarithm of the stock market transaction value, as indicators of financial development, on private sector growth is positive and statistically significant. However, the impact of the logarithm of the credit to the private sector/GDP ratio, as a measure of financial depth, on private sector growth is neither positive nor statistically significant.

Table 7. Partial Error Correction Coefficients for the Cointegration Vector

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-Statistic	Status
lnprGDpt(-1)	1.00000	-----	-----	-----
lnMt(-1)	0.944	0.290	3.255	Significant
lnBCt(-1)	0.302	0.331	0.912	Insignificant
lnSt(-1)	0.421	0.107	3.920	Significant
lnGt(-1)	-46.62	11.169	-4.177	Significant
lnIt(-1)	0.943	0.221	4.267	Significant
lnTOt(-1)	0.153	0.004	3.825	Significant
Dt(-1)	-0.119	0.120	-0.992	Insignificant

Furthermore, the impact of the control variables is as follows: the logarithm of the government consumption expenditure/GDP ratio on private sector growth is negative and statistically significant, indicating a crowding-out effect; the logarithm of the private sector investment/GDP ratio on private sector growth is positive and statistically significant, suggesting that the volume of investment plays a fundamental role in private sector growth; and the trade openness index also has a positive and statistically significant impact on private sector growth. Finally, the impact of the dummy variable for the ISIS war conditions on private sector growth shows a negative sign, but statistically, it is not significant.

Analysis of Dynamics in the Research Model

To examine the dynamics between the variables of the research model, two criteria are used: the impulse response function and variance decomposition. In Figure (2), the impulse responses of private sector growth to changes in financial development indicators, measured by one standard deviation shocks, are depicted.

Figure 2. Examination of the Impulse Response Function of Private Sector Growth to Changes in Financial Development Indicators

On the left side of Figure (2), the impacts of the logarithm of the total money supply/GDP ratio on private sector growth are depicted. Accordingly, with an impulse of one standard deviation in the logarithm of the total money supply/GDP ratio as a financial development indicator, the private sector growth trend is highly volatile until the eighth period, after which the volatility subsides starting from the ninth period.

On the right side of Figure (2), the effects of the logarithm of the stock market transaction value, as a financial development indicator, on private sector growth are shown. Based on this, with an impulse of one standard deviation in the logarithm of the stock market transaction value, the growth trend of the private sector is highly volatile until the seventh period, and from the eighth period onward, the volatility decreases.

In Figure (3), the impulse responses of private sector growth to changes in the financial depth indicator are depicted, with one standard deviation shocks.

Figure 3. Examination of the Impulse Response Function of Private Sector Growth to Changes in the Financial Depth Indicator

In Figure (3), the impacts of the logarithm of the credit to the private sector/GDP ratio, as a financial depth indicator, on private sector growth are depicted. Accordingly, with an impulse of one standard deviation in the logarithm of the credit to the private sector/GDP ratio as a financial depth indicator, the private sector growth trend is highly volatile.

However, in Table (8), the contribution of each of the financial development indicators, financial depth, and other variables in the research model to the growth rate of the private sector over a ten-year period is presented. According to the results in Table (8), private sector growth has the most significant effect on itself in the first period, and in the tenth period, 97.067% of the error variance in private sector growth is explained by its own growth and financial development indicators, including: the logarithm of the total money supply/GDP ratio (lnMt) and the logarithm of the stock market transaction value (lnSt), with respective impacts of 0.118% and 0.026%. The logarithm of the credit to the private sector/GDP ratio, as a financial depth indicator (lnBCt), has an impact of 0.008%. The impact of the control variables—logarithm of the government consumption expenditure/GDP ratio, logarithm of the private sector investment/GDP ratio, and the trade openness index in the tenth period on private sector growth is 0.0603, 0.0468, and 2.7854, respectively. The impact of the ISIS war conditions in the tenth period on private sector growth is 0.0021.

Table 8. Forecast Error Decomposition of Private Sector Growth Using Variance Decomposition Method

Period	S .D	lnprGDpt	(lnMt)	(lnSt)	(lnBCt)	lnGt	lnIt	lnTOt	Dt
1	0.565	100.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
2	0.599	97.9750	0.0140	0.0002	0.0161	0.0366	0.0051	1.9504	0.0028
3	0.651	97.0830	0.0119	0.0002	0.0153	0.0377	0.0856	2.7638	0.0029
4	0.726	97.5580	0.0118	0.0005	0.0296	0.0668	0.0689	2.2624	0.0023
5	0.772	97.2020	0.0182	0.0005	0.0313	0.0630	0.0612	2.6211	0.0028
6	0.821	97.1040	0.0163	0.0007	0.0285	0.0596	0.0591	2.7292	0.0026
7	0.869	97.1160	0.0152	0.0008	0.0318	0.0689	0.0528	2.7118	0.0024
8	0.912	97.1040	0.0138	0.0007	0.0291	0.0645	0.0518	2.7341	0.0023
9	0.954	97.0880	0.0128	0.0008	0.0274	0.0617	0.0499	2.7567	0.0022
10	0.994	97.0670	0.0118	0.0008	0.0260	0.0603	0.0468	2.7854	0.0021

Conclusion and Recommendations

A developed financial system, alongside various factors that affect it, significantly depends on the volume and share of private sector activities and investments in the overall economy. In fact, the existence of a developed financial market and its flourishing is based on the level of demand in this market, which is driven by investors. Naturally, the higher the growth of the private sector in the economy, the greater the demand for capital resources in financial markets, and this plays a crucial role in the development of financial markets and the formation of their components. Therefore, this study examines the impact of financial development on the growth of the private sector in an oil-dependent economy in Iraq for the years 2008 to 2022, using the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM).

Based on the results of the model estimation using the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM), the impact of the logarithm of the total money supply/GDP ratio and the logarithm of the stock market transaction value, as financial development indicators, on private sector growth is positive and significant, confirming the first hypothesis. Therefore, if the total money supply and the stock market transaction value lead to private sector growth, the results of the first hypothesis test align with the studies of Dart et al. (2005), Masiha et al. (2009), Dua (2014), Law and Moradbeigi (2017), Emadulhaq (2020), Levin and Zerrouk (1998), Kooki (2013), Ibrahim (2013), and Rahman (2018). Additionally, according to the results of the model estimation using VECM, the impact of the logarithm of the credit to the private sector/GDP ratio, as a financial depth indicator, on private sector growth is positive but insignificant. Therefore, the results of testing the second hypothesis do not align with the studies of Emadulhaq (2020) and Beck (2011).

Given the positive and significant impact of financial development indicators on private sector growth in Iraq, and considering the country's oil-based economic structure and institutional challenges, the following recommendations are proposed:

- The Iraqi government should strengthen regulatory institutions, enhance financial transparency, and improve corporate governance in order to create an appropriate institutional framework for financial development, thereby enabling sustainable private sector growth.
- It is essential to adopt supportive policies such as facilitating private sector access to financial resources, developing capital markets, and improving the banking system to increase the efficiency of financial intermediation—particularly in non-oil sectors—to promote economic diversification and reduce dependence on oil.

However, Given Iraq's oil-dependent economic structure and the underperformance of its banking system in financing the private sector, the findings indicate that while the financial depth indicator has a positive effect on private sector growth, this effect is statistically insignificant. This suggests that Iraqi banks have not played an effective role in supporting productive activities and private sector investment. In light of Iraq's economic needs, the following recommendations are proposed:

- The Central Bank of Iraq should design and implement targeted policies to strengthen the connection between the banking system and the private sector—particularly by directing financial resources toward productive projects in non-oil sectors.
- Moreover, considering the volatility of oil revenues, it is essential for the Central Bank to adopt stable and prudent monetary policies. These policies should aim to reduce excessive fluctuations in financial markets, while creating a suitable environment for the expansion of formal financial markets and enhancing investor confidence.

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